

ELIXIR Commissioned Service DATAREX WP3

Deliverables 3.1 & 3.2 First versions (MVP) of the knowledge handbook and the maturity model for RDM services providers

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the Minimum Viable Products (MVP) of the Data Stewardship Handbook (DSH) and the RDM services Maturity Model (MM), developed within ELIXIR DATAREX Work Package 3, to support capacity building for Research Data Management (RDM) services across ELIXIR Nodes and Institutes.

ELIXIR Nodes operate in diverse institutional and national contexts but face similar challenges in organising and sustaining RDM services. Prior to DATAREX, there was no shared structure or common terminology at ELIXIR level to describe RDM service provision and practical guidance was scattered across projects, platforms and local initiatives. The objective of this work was to provide a shared, non-prescriptive framework and accompanying guidance that can be applied across different contexts. The MM addresses this by defining core areas of RDM service provision through indicators and maturity levels. The DSH complements the model by providing practical explanations, community examples, and links to supporting resources.

The resources were developed through dedicated workshops and contentathons, fulfilling Work Package 3 milestones M3.1 and M3.2 and delivering Work Package 3 outputs D3.1 and D3.2. Both resources together are currently openly available as an MVP and they provide ELIXIR Nodes and Institutes with a shared starting point for developing and improving RDM services beyond the RDM Community DATAREX Implementation Study.

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Document Info

Responsible Participant	Mijke Jetten (Netherlands - Health-RI Foundation) Ivan Mičetić (Italy - University of Padova)
Dissemination level	Public

Author List

Node	Institution* (please choose from the list above)	Name, surname	ORCID
NL-Netherlands	Netherlands - Health-RI Foundation	Mijke, Jetten	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9114-2896
IT-Italy	Italy - University of Padova	Ivan, Mičetić	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1691-8425
Reviewer 1	UK - Earlham Institute	Xènia, Pérez-Sitjà	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7166-0183
Reviewer 2	Belgium - VIB vzw (VIB)	Flora, D'Anna	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4665-6673
Reviewer 3	UK - University of Manchester	Munazah, Andrabi	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7718-5109

Abbreviations and Acronyms

DSH	Data Stewardship Handbook
MM	Maturity Model
RDM	Research Data Management
MVP	Minimal Viable Product

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Overview of Workshops and Contentathons

Event	Date	Location	Aim	Main results
December 2023 Bergen workshop	4-6 December 2023	Bergen	Explore needs of data stewards. Discuss gaps across Nodes and Institutes. Introduce the first idea for shared guidance	First concept for a handbook. Early agreement that a common resource is needed. Seed for the DSH
May 2024 online contentathon	21, 22, 28, 29 May 2024	Online	Start drafting the Handbook. Create first outlines. Review introductory pages. Identify core topics	Early outlines. Draft welcome and contribute pages. Shared structure
December 2024 Luxembourg workshop	2-5 December 2024	Luxembourg	Improve structure. Build example pages. Prepare technical setup for publication	Example chapter. Stronger layout. Initial GitHub setup
March 2025 Bari workshop	24-26 March 2025	Bari	Refine the Maturity Model. Clarify domains and	Updated model. Agreed domain structure. First guidance text

Event	Date	Location	Aim	Main results
			indicators. Draft initial guidance	
May 2025 Tartu workshop	19-22 May 2025	Tartu	Apply the model. Draft more guidance. Connect model and handbook with training work	Additional guidance. More complete chapters. Template validation
September 2025 Ghent workshop	22-24 September 2025	Ghent	Review progress. Harmonise text. Identify final gaps. Plan remaining steps for MVP	Consolidated chapters. Agreed list of missing elements. Clear direction toward MVP
November 2025 BioHackathon project	3-7 November 2025	Berlin	Improve content. Improve design and UI/UX. Move content to Github	Refined indicator descriptions. First MVP with usability in mind
December 2025 online contentathon	3, 10, 15 December 2025	Online	Final review and alignment. Most content moved to Github. Proper basis for MVP	Coherent MVP of the Handbook. Updated content with draft texts. Stable structure for GitHub

Table 1. Green = DSH focused activity; Orange = MM focused activity; Blue = mixed DSH and MM activity

Background and Purpose

The Data Stewardship Handbook (DSH) and the Maturity Model (MM) were developed within the ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) Community as part of the DATAREX Implementation Study. During this work, ELIXIR Nodes and Institutes identified the need for a shared reference to clarify the key areas of RDM service provision and to reflect on existing support structures. Earlier ELIXIR activities on RDM strategy development had already highlighted the value of a common conceptual framework.

While existing resources like RDMkit provide guidelines, best practices, tools, and examples, they target researchers, scientists, and policymakers, in addition to RDM

professionals, and focus on practical, immediately applicable guidance (“how to do it now”). In contrast, DHS is specifically designed for RDM professionals delivering institutional services and emphasises guidance, examples, and use cases aimed at improving workflows and practices over time (“how to improve”).

The MM and the DSH were conceived and developed in parallel through an iterative process of workshops and contentathons (see table above). The maturity model defines the core areas of RDM services through a set of indicators, while the Handbook provides concise explanations, examples, and practical guidance for these same areas. Drafting and refining Handbook content helped sharpen the indicators, and updates to the model informed the Handbook’s structure. Together, they form a single, integrated resource in which the model and the Handbook strengthen one another.

The purpose of this joint deliverable is to present the first complete versions of both resources. The MM supports Nodes and Institutes in assessing their current level of RDM service provision, while the DSH offers initial guidance and starting points for further development. The DSH is maintained in a public [GitHub repository](#) while the MM is maintained in a [separate GitHub repository](#) that automatically populates the MM pages of the Handbook. Both are available for users via the [DSH website](#) and serve as a shared basis for continued, community-driven development within the ELIXIR RDM Community.

Maturity Model

The MM provides a shared structure that gives a clear overview of what RDM service provision can include and allows users to reflect on their current level of development in a consistent way. The model is not used for evaluation or comparison but as a practical tool for planning, internal alignment and discussions with diverse stakeholders.

Why a maturity model

Nodes and Institutes need a simple, shared vocabulary for describing RDM support. Not all Nodes and Institutes have the same structure, but the same types of RDM activities exist across all. Without a model, conversations start from scratch each time. With the MM, Nodes and Institutes can quickly map their situation to a known structure, see gaps and overlaps and discuss priorities in a more grounded way. The MM and the DSH are designed to be used together for a senior subset of users: the model offers a structured set of indicators for reflection and self-assessment, while the Handbook provides short guidance pages that explain concepts, share success examples and point to supporting

resources. The resources reinforce each other, without requiring the Handbook to mirror the model one-to-one.

Structure of the model

The MM currently contains 25 indicators, grouped into **four domains**:

- **Strategy and sustainability:** covers the organisational elements required to support RDM. Examples include strategy for RDM, personnel for RDM, and data governance and alignment with policies.
- **Legal and governance:** covers policy, data protection, ethics and IT security aspects. Indicators include legal framework for research data, IT security for research data and data protection compliance.
- **RDM support:** describes the services, guidance and communication provided to researchers. Indicators are for instance training, training materials, expert networks and flow of communication.
- **Data and metadata management:** Covers standards, tools and infrastructure throughout the data life cycle. Examples include RDM software tools and resources, standards for documentation, data publication and data management planning support.

How the model works

Each indicator is described through maturity levels, usually 1 to 4. Levels show how developed an element of RDM support can be, from minimal or ad-hoc practices to structured, well-established and integrated ones. These maturity descriptions make progress visible in small, realistic steps and help Nodes and Institutes identify what “the next logical improvement” might be for them.

Concrete example

Domain: RDM Support

Indicator: RDM Training

- **Level 1:** No RDM training offered to staff
- **Level 2:** Ad-hoc RDM training provided, no or limited targeted approach
- **Level 3:** Regular training and/or broad audience reach with targeted contents
- **Level 4:** Structured program and train-the-trainer is made available to internal trainers

This example shows how the model breaks a broad concept into manageable stages. The indicator is not prescriptive; it simply describes typical steps. Nodes and Institutes decide for themselves where they stand and where to develop. An indicator or a specific maturity level may also not be relevant or appropriate for a given Node or Institute, depending on its context and scope.

Data Stewardship Handbook

The DSH brings together practical guidance, community examples and the MM in one place. It helps Nodes and Institutes understand what different RDM topics involve in practice and supports reflection on RDM service provision.

The current version of the Handbook is a Minimum Viable Product (MVP). Most pages are first drafts. Content from documents, workshops and contentathons is still being moved into the site and reviewed. Several topics need clearer explanations, examples from Nodes and Institutes or stronger links to existing ELIXIR resources. Technical adjustments are also ongoing to improve page layout, headings, navigation and internal consistency. The MVP approach makes the material available early, gives contributors something concrete to react to and establishes a structure that can be expanded.

Why a Handbook

Nodes and Institutes need accessible, practice-oriented material to support their work on RDM services. While the MM provides a shared structure for reflection and self-assessment, the Handbook adds explanations, community examples and links to practical resources. Together, they provide a shared starting point for Nodes and Institutes as they develop or improve their RDM services.

Structure of the Handbook

The Handbook is organised as a guided journey through the landscape of research data management support, with the magpie, the DSH mascot and guide, helping visitors discover and navigate key concepts. Rather than presenting long, linear text, the Handbook uses three main landmarks that correspond to ways people explore and learn on the site.

- **Signposts** are the first landmarks encountered on this journey. They offer step-by-step advice and simple tools to help users manage research data. These pages provide a quick orientation to a topic, with concise explanations and

pointers to relevant considerations, making them helpful in starting or refreshing understanding without needing a deep-dive background explanation.

- **Campfires** are places to gather and learn from others. These pages collect stories and case studies from across the community, showing real-world examples of how different Nodes and Institutes have addressed RDM topics. Campfires make abstract ideas concrete and allow readers to compare their own situation with those of others, learning from lived experience.
- **Waypoints** act as markers along the route. They represent maturity indicators used for self-assessment and are derived from the MM. Each waypoint corresponds to a specific indicator and outlines the core elements associated with that topic. Handbook pages link to these waypoints, offering short explanations and contextual information that help Nodes and Institutes understand how their own RDM services relate to recognised stages of development.

Together, these landmarks (Signposts, Campfires and Waypoints) support exploration, comparison and progress, allowing each Node to navigate the Handbook in ways that fit their context and goals.

User journeys and design considerations

The structure of the Handbook is informed by explicit user journeys developed during [BioHackathon 2025 \(Project #2\)](#). These journeys were used as a design tool to understand how different groups involved in RDM support are likely to interact with the resource and to ensure that the Handbook supports multiple entry points rather than a single linear pathway.

Three broad user profiles were considered during this work: junior data stewards, senior data stewards, and coordination or strategy roles. These profiles are not intended as public-facing roles, but as a way to prioritise content types and navigation patterns. In practice, users move between these roles or combine aspects of several profiles.

As a result, the Handbook is structured so that users can approach topics through short guidance pages, community case studies, or maturity indicators depending on their needs. Cross-linking between these elements allows users to relate practical examples to conceptual guidance and to reflect on their own level of service maturity without requiring a strict one-to-one mapping between Handbook pages and maturity indicators.

How the Handbook works

The Handbook supports learning and discussion by combining short guidance, community examples and maturity indicators. Readers can explore topics through Signposts and Campfires and use the Waypoints to relate this information to their own context. The Handbook supports reflection and planning without requiring a one-to-one mapping between Handbook pages and maturity indicators.

Concrete example

A Node exploring improvements to its RDM training offering can consult Signposts for basic guidance, review Campfire examples from other Nodes and Institutes, and relate these insights to the RDM training Waypoint derived from the MM. This illustrates how the Handbook helps translate maturity indicators into practical considerations.

Outcomes and Expected Impact

The MM and DSH provide ELIXIR Nodes and Institutes with a shared, practical foundation for describing, assessing and developing RDM service provision in a consistent, context-sensitive way. Together, they address previously identified gaps in shared structure, vocabulary, and practical guidance for RDM services across diverse institutional contexts.

Outcomes

This work delivered two closely connected resources that support capacity building for RDM services in ELIXIR Nodes and Institutes.

- The MM provides a non-prescriptive framework with clearly defined indicators and maturity levels, supporting reflection, planning and internal alignment rather than evaluation or comparison.
- The DSH complements the model with practical guidance, short explanations, community examples and links to supporting resources. The current version is explicitly published as a MVP. Both resources are openly available through a sustainable technical setup that supports reuse and versioning across Nodes and Institutes.

To build on these outcomes, further development would require a dedicated follow up effort, clear ownership and allocated capacity and modest funding for activities such as workshops and contentathons. In the absence of these elements, continued evolution

of the resources currently depends on voluntary community engagement via e.g. the future ELIXIR RDM Community joint activities.

Expected impact

In the short to medium term, the MM and DSH are expected to:

- Reduce fragmentation in how RDM services are described and discussed across ELIXIR Nodes and Institutes.
- Support more efficient internal alignment and clearer onboarding of RDM professionals.
- Strengthen Node level capacity to plan and incrementally improve RDM services using a shared language and visible practices.

In the longer term, the resources contribute to a more coherent and mature RDM service landscape across ELIXIR and support alignment with ELIXIR strategies for FAIR RDM services and Open Science objectives. The extent and pace of this impact will depend on sustained community engagement and the availability of structural support and funding beyond the DATAREX Implementation Study.

Dissemination Plan

This report will be uploaded to Zenodo within the ELIXIR Zenodo Community. As stated earlier, the MM and DSH itself are available via the [DSH website](#) and serve as a shared basis for continued, community driven development and use within the ELIXIR RDM Community. The MM itself is also [archived](#) to ensure long-term accessibility and citation.

List of Tables

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